

Analysis of the 3M Technique Approach Through Al-Ghazali's Theory in Helping Manage Emotional Pressure

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Emotional pressure; Al-Ghazali's theory; spirituality	Emotional pressure can be defined as a reaction caused by a burden imposed on an individual. Pressure or stress is also a physical, emotional, and mental response experienced by an individual when demands cannot be met. However, excessive stress over a prolonged period and not properly managed can lead to negative effects that may harm health. There are various causes of emotional pressure among students, including learning issues, family conflicts, and peer relationships. This case study focuses on the problems faced by a Form 1 student at a school in the state of Melaka who is experiencing emotional pressure. This case study aims to examine the effectiveness of Al-Ghazali's counseling theory in helping manage the student's emotional pressure and addressing the issue. This study employs a qualitative approach using observation, interviews, and document analysis. The findings indicate that the student's emotional pressure stems from family tensions, leading the student to isolate themselves, rebel, and cry frequently. This issue is also related to spiritual aspects, which can be connected to Al-Ghazali's approach. The application of Al-Ghazali's counseling theory intervention is effective in helping manage the student's emotional pressure.

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1. Introduction

According to an article published by UPM in April 2023, mental health issues show an increase, with statistics of individuals seeking support through the Psychosocial Support Service Helpline (MHPSS), an initiative under the National Centre of Excellence for Mental Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia (KKM), increasing fivefold in 2022 compared to 2020. The National Health and Morbidity Survey (NHMS) shows that 1 in 4 teenagers experienced symptoms of depression in 2022 compared to 1 in 5 teenagers in 2019 (Media Statement of the Ministry of Health Malaysia, 2023).

Pressure or stress is a condition where an individual bears a burden that is difficult to endure [14]. According to the Fourth Edition of Kamus Dewan, pressure is defined as a state of anxiety, worry, and tension caused by mental or physical strain. Pressure does not only attack from an emotional aspect but also in physical form [15]. In addition, pressure is a condition influenced by mental and emotional disturbances that can lead to an unstable or tense situation if it is not well controlled by the individual. Pressure often occurs when someone faces a situation that is difficult or unacceptable to their mind and body [16][17].

Emotion, on the other hand, is an inner feeling that arises in a person due to their reaction to an experience, event, or situation. According to Daniel Goleman (2006), there are various emotions within a person, and they are divided into several types, such as surprise, sadness, anger, and many more. A person has both good and bad emotions that arise from their heart based on experiences or situations they go through. Negative emotions arise when a person lacks the strength of faith, especially in difficult and tense situations. This causes a person to have negative views of themselves, those around them, or their environment, even questioning the fate determined by God [20].

According to Andriyani (2019), from the Islamic perspective, emotional pressure is also a state where a person's soul is in an unhealthy or uneasy situation, such as sadness, anxiety, disappointment, and anger [15]. Islamic psychologists such as Imam al-Ghazali, Muhammad Uthman Najati, and Muhammad Izzudin Taufik believe that unstable or unsettled emotions, that is, emotional pressure, are caused by a person's failure to connect themselves with God, Allah S.W.T. Instead, they follow their desires alone. Therefore, an appropriate approach in the Islamic context can treat an individual's emotional pressure [20]. Moreover, emotional pressure is also a crisis or a major contributor to a person's self-development. This is because emotions also influence an individual's decisions and actions in life [9].

In this study, the researcher applies Al-Ghazali's counseling theory from the model of Tajudin Ninggal [11], where this theory takes the philosophical thought of Al-Ghazali based on the Quran and Hadith, emphasizing that the ultimate goal of humans is to achieve the level of insan kamil. Insan kamil can be interpreted as a perfect human in terms of spirituality, which can be attained through faith in God, worship, and good conduct.

1.1 Problem Statement

The balanced development in determining students' direction is highly emphasized, as stated in the National Education Philosophy (FPK):

"Education in Malaysia is an ongoing effort towards further developing an individual's potential in a comprehensive and integrated manner to create a balanced and harmonious person in terms of intellect, spirituality, emotions, and physical aspects, based on belief and obedience to God. This effort aims to produce Malaysian citizens who are knowledgeable, skilled, noble in character, responsible, and capable of achieving personal well-being, as well as contributing to the harmony and prosperity of the family, society, and the nation."

(Ministry of Education Malaysia)

Based on the FPK above, the aspects of intellect, spirituality, emotions, and physical well-being are crucial within an individual. The effort to create individuals who firmly adhere to religious teachings will be achieved by emphasizing all these aspects to develop a balanced human character. These aspects are essential in forming a well-rounded and balanced individual and preventing undesirable occurrences. One of the critical aspects is an individual's emotional state. Failure to control emotions makes one easily influenced by negative elements, causing them to disregard the teachings they have learned. Consequently, students may experience emotional disturbances due to their inability to cope with the problems they face [14].

To address the research question, a male Form 1 student in a school in Melaka who experienced emotional stress was identified by the researcher. The student was selected as a research participant for this case study. This is because the participant displayed unmotivated behavior in class. He would sit alone and was not active in speaking with classmates. During group activities, the participant would only sit and observe without engaging in discussions or saying anything. The participant also had moments where he suddenly cried and acted out during teaching and learning sessions (PdP). The researcher attempted to calm the participant and called a male teacher to bring him to the counseling and guidance unit. Subsequently, the researcher consulted the guidance and counseling teacher to gain further insight into the student's condition and issues.

After identifying the cause, the researcher conducted an intervention by applying Al-Ghazali's counseling theory and assessing its effectiveness in addressing emotional stress among students. The researcher hopes that implementing this intervention will have a positive impact on the findings of this case study and help the participant manage his emotional stress.

1.2 Objectives

1. Identifying the causes contributing to emotional stress among students.
2. Analyzing the effectiveness of Imam Al-Ghazali's counseling theory in reducing emotional stress among students.

1.3 Research Question

1. What are the causes contributing to emotional stress among students?
2. Is Imam Al-Ghazali's Counseling Theory effective in reducing emotional stress among students?

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The design for this study is qualitative, using a case study approach. The data collected by the researcher is through observation, interviews, and document analysis. According to Sutikno & Hadisaputra (2021), qualitative research is a method used to examine and understand the behavior of individuals or groups [5]. Additionally, it aims to gain a deeper understanding of a particular matter or phenomenon and unravel the ways and reasons why that phenomenon occurs. Furthermore, qualitative research is a way to understand and explore a group or individual experiencing an issue. The data collection methods in this case study, such as observation and interviews, are suitable and effective [5].

2.2 Sampling

The sampling for this study is non-probability sampling, which is a non-random method commonly used in qualitative research. This non-random sampling is taken from a group that has been

identified based on specific characteristics. The researcher used a convenience sampling method, where the researcher selected participants they encountered and were most familiar with. In this study, the researcher met and consulted with the school counselor to gather further information about the emotional stress issues among students in the school. However, the school was also dealing with students experiencing emotional stress from various causes, involving Form 1 students. Therefore, the researcher selected one of them who was experiencing emotional stress to cooperate and share information related to the causes of emotional stress. The researcher focused on a male Form 1 student who was also taught by the researcher in the Islamic Education subject. This was also under the guidance and monitoring of the school counselor. This facilitated the researcher in obtaining information regarding the causes of emotional stress for this student. The student was selected based on the criteria and requirements set in this study.

2.3 Instruments, Validity, and Reliability

The researcher used the observation method effectively in the classroom as an instrument. This was to assist the researcher in recording more detailed information. Sutikno & Hadisaputra (2020) define observation as a process where the researcher or observer watches the study situation [5]. For a month, the researcher observed the student's actual behavior during teaching and learning sessions (PdP). Therefore, this information was used during the interview session with the student. After the observation period, the researcher concluded that the student was experiencing emotional stress. This conclusion was made because the student isolated himself and remained silent during the PdP sessions. Additionally, during group activities, the student did not show positive or active participation.

Next, the data collection process also involved document analysis by the researcher. Document analysis is a method that provides an overview and explanation of the student's mental health status through the analysis of the DASS (Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale) test results obtained. According to Norazlinda Muda, a Psychologist Officer from the Human Resource Division, USM Registrar Department, the DASS test is a screening tool used to identify an individual's level of depression, anxiety, and stress. It also functions as an initial screening for mental health, with the need for diagnosis by a medical professional [18].

Table 1
Student's DASS Scale

	Score	Level
Depression	10.00	Moderate
Anxiety	8.00	Moderate
Stress	10.00	Moderate

In addition, one of the instruments used to gather information in this study is the interview method. The interview was conducted with a male student experiencing emotional stress, and the researcher will analyze the data carefully. Furthermore, the researcher also employed an unstructured interview method in this study, allowing flexibility in asking questions according to the situation. According to Haridi, Ismail, Jodi, & Aleh (2021), the researcher can obtain various information from the study participants through open-ended questions [10].

The validity of the instrument is crucial in determining whether an instrument is appropriate for measuring the study participants. Validity and reliability are among the important aspects that need to be emphasized in determining the suitability and accuracy of items in the instruments of a study [15]. Othman, Ghazali, Zabit & Hadi (2020) explain that reliability is a process for testing the consistency of the instrument used in the study [5]. The accuracy of the obtained information can help produce a good instrument through validity and reliability. As stated by Hashim, Surat & Zulkifli

(2023), the validity and reliability of the study instrument are essential tools in measuring the extent to which the instrument used in data collection is valid and reliable [15].

3. Findings and Discussion

3.1 Causes Contributing to Emotional Stress Among Students

The data analysis was carried out based on two research questions: identifying the factors contributing to emotional stress among the study participants and determining the effectiveness of Imam Al-Ghazali's counseling theory in managing emotional stress in students.

Through observation, the researcher found that the student frequently isolated themselves, avoided interacting with classmates, and showed little involvement during classroom activities, including group work. However, the researcher noted that changes in the student's behavior were visible after the implementation of Imam Al-Ghazali's counseling theory.

From the interview conducted, the participant shared that they started facing emotional stress at the beginning of 2023. Below is an excerpt from the interview:

Time: 13:23

Researcher: "Are you okay? How are you feeling now?"

Participant: "I don't know, teacher. I feel stressed."

Researcher: "Why? What's making you feel stressed? Can you tell me about it?"

Participant: "My dad had a stroke and can't walk. My mom left us, teacher. She works somewhere else. After school, I go buy stuff to cook, take care of my dad and my siblings at home. I'm the one who goes to the bank to take out my dad's money to buy things. Sometimes my uncle comes by to check on us. I don't have time to study. After school, I do my homework. At school, I feel jealous seeing my friends happy with their families. They get picked up and dropped off by their parents, but I walk alone, through the rain or the sun. I feel like everything is unfair to me, teacher. That's why I don't like to make friends. I feel like I'm lacking. I'm not like the others. I feel insecure talking. I miss my mom. I miss how things used to be, with my dad healthy and working, and my mom cooking for us. But now everything has changed. I feel sad sometimes, and I just feel angry."

Based on the participant's response, the emotional stress they were facing was primarily due to family tension. Additionally, this emotional stress also interfered with the participant's focus on studies. According to Rose & Mustaffa (2018), family relationships that are cold or dysfunctional can negatively affect a child's development [20]. Emotional stress can also arise from marital conflicts, sibling issues, or conflicts between parents and children. Any of these conflicts can lead to negative emotions such as disappointment, anger, sadness, depression, and hurt feelings.

Significant family changes, such as the death of a family member, divorce, or health problems, can cause noticeable emotional stress in students. Zainuddin & Salleh (2022) stated that emotional stress originating from family issues can become a major factor in a student's emotional and psychological life [16]. The family plays a vital role in shaping a student's identity, well-being, and emotional balance.

3.2 Effectiveness of Imam Al-Ghazali's Counseling Theory in Reducing Emotional Stress Among Students

According to Omar & Ninggal (2019), it is stated that the philosophy of Al-Ghazali's thinking is based on the Quran and Hadith as the main reference sources [15]. From the spiritual aspect of the human self, it helps a person return to God and change towards achieving the status of *insan kamil*. According to Al-Ghazali, humans need to be understood from both their physical and spiritual aspects. This needs to be applied with the spiritual element in counseling, as it is not a new effort. This is because the various problems faced by an individual are not only caused by physical aspects. They also stem from the spiritual aspect, especially related to the heart and emotions [15].

Humans who lack an understanding of the meaning of life based on religion will cause a person not to accept their life circumstances. According to Mohd Abbas Abdul Razak (2013), Islam is a guide for humans to achieve balance in fulfilling both physical and spiritual needs [12]. The balance of these two demands is crucial in producing a healthy soul [20]. The counseling session conducted in this study used Al-Ghazali's counseling theory from the model of Tajudin Ninggal through three processes, which are [11]:

3.2.1 *Muhasabah (Self-Reflection)*

Muhasabah refers to the process of self-reflection and self-assessment to evaluate a person's actions and behaviors, especially in the context of spiritual life and morals. The process of *Muhasabah* requires a deep examination of a person's actions, intentions, and attitudes, as well as consideration of whether these actions align with the values of Islamic ethics and spirituality. The goal is to raise self-awareness, detect and correct mistakes, and improve behavior to better align with religious principles. By engaging in *Muhasabah* regularly and well, a person can improve themselves and enhance their relationship with God [5].

Initially, the researcher incorporated film therapy to carry out the *Muhasabah* process. Watching a movie or video can help a person recognize their connection with the situations and characters in the film, leading to personal exploration and reflection, as well as controlling emotions from experiences that cause them stress [19].

The researcher conducted the *Muhasabah* intervention by showing a short film titled "*Tanah Kubur*" as film therapy for the participant. This activity was meant to first attract the participant's interest and attention. Then, the researcher asked several questions. Some of the questions included:

1. Based on the video earlier, what mistakes were made?
2. What were the consequences faced by the character?
3. What is the ruling on performing prayers?
4. What is the ruling on respecting or being courteous to others, especially parents?
5. What about you? Do you perform prayers? Do you treat your parents well?

The participant answered these questions based on the video they watched earlier. The researcher also asked the participant to reflect on themselves, to do *Muhasabah* based on the short film. The participant responded by saying, "Teacher, I've been neglecting my prayers, I only pray at school. I don't want to get sins, I want to earn rewards... taking care of my father, sometimes I complain, why do I have to take care of him? I feel stressed at that moment..."

3.2.2 *Musyaratah (Setting Conditions)*

According to Hasanah (2018), it is stated that *Musyaratah* is the establishment of conditions for performing important deeds or practices to become a good Muslim [5]. In this process, it is also emphasized that a person should always be aware of Allah SWT. This makes it necessary for a person to implement the conditions that have been set. Additionally, it serves to set conditions to ensure the soul remains on the path that is pleasing to Allah SWT and His Messenger.

The researcher conducted the intervention by providing a list of commendable deeds for the student to follow over three weeks. The participant also carried out the suggested intervention according to the guidance provided by the researcher. The participant was asked to mark the box if they carried out the action or task. If the participant did not do it, the box should remain empty. Below is the list of deeds successfully carried out by the participant, along with the graph showing the participant's progress in carrying out this intervention.

SENARAI AMALAN MURID HEBAT -MINGGU 1

BIL	PERKARA	HARI						
		ISNIN	SELASA	RABU	KHAMIS	JUMAAT	SABTU	AHAD
1	SOLAT SUBUH		✓	✓				
2	SOLAT ZOHOR	✓	✓		✓	✓		
3	SOLAT ASAR							
4	SOLAT MAGHRIB					✓		✓
5	SOLAT ISYA'		✓			✓		✓

Figure 1. List of Deeds for the First Week

SENARAI AMALAN MURID HEBAT -MINGGU 2

BIL	HARI							
	PERKARA	ISNIN	SELASA	RABU	KHAMIS	JUMAAT	SABTU	AHAD
1	SOLAT SUBUH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
2	SOLAT ZOHOR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
3	SOLAT ASAR				✓			
4	SOLAT MAGHRIB	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
5	SOLAT ISYA'	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
6	BACA QURAN (SEKURANGNYA 5 AYAT)	✓			✓	✓		
7	ZIKIR	✓				✓		
8	DOA (PENENANG HATI, IBU BAPA, KEJAYAAN & REZEKI DUNIA AKHIRAT)	✓			✓			

Figure 2. List of Deeds for the Second Week

SENARAI AMALAN MURID HEBAT -MINGGU 3

BIL	HARI							
	PERKARA	ISNIN	SELASA	RABU	KHAMIS	JUMAAT	SABTU	AHAD
1	SOLAT SUBUH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	SOLAT ZOHOR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
3	SOLAT ASAR	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
4	SOLAT MAGHRIB	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
5	SOLAT ISYA'	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
6	BACA QURAN (SEKURANGNYA 5 AYAT)	✓	✓		✓	✓		
7	ZIKIR	✓	✓		✓	✓		
8	DOA (PENENANG HATI, IBU BAPA, KEJAYAAN & REZEKI DUNIA AKHIRAT)	✓		✓	✓	✓		
9	BANTU AYAH & ADIK DI RUMAH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
10	PERKARA BAIK YANG DILAKUKAN (CTH: BANTU KAWAN, TOLONG CIKGU, SENYUM DAN MENEGUR ORANG SEKELILING DAN LAIN2 NYATAKAN)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

Figure 3. List of Deeds for the Third Week

Figure 4. Participant Achievement Graph (Prayer)

Figure 5. Participant Achievement Graph (Quran, Dhikr & Prayer)

Based on the list of practices form and achievement graph over the 3 weeks, the researcher can conclude that there was an improvement and change made by the participant. Although not all practices were completed, there was still progress from week to week. This indicates a positive change and impact on the participant. It also clearly shows that the participant was able to control and manage their emotional stress well by performing the actions and practices of a good Muslim.

3.2.3 Mujahadah

Mujahadah is an Arabic term that means effort or struggle. In the context of Islam, *mujahadah* refers to the efforts or struggles of a Muslim to improve themselves, uphold religious values, and perform obedience to Allah. *Mujahadah* encompasses various aspects of life, including spiritual, moral, and social aspects. It is also linked to the concept of striving to overcome temptations, restraining oneself from committing sinful acts, and enhancing the quality of worship [11].

In this process, the researcher observed every Monday, Tuesday, Thursday, and Friday during the Islamic Education classes. The researcher observed that the participants were determined to improve themselves. This is because there was an improvement in the list of good deeds over the 3 weeks implemented by the participants. The participants showed effort (*mujahadah*) in carrying out the intervention, where they sincerely performed their daily prayers, even though initially, they felt it was difficult due to laziness, tiredness, and other reasons. However, due to their desire to change, the participants earnestly performed them. The researcher also constantly asked about the participants' condition and included elements of advice.

Additionally, the participants also made efforts to meet with the researcher to listen to their recitation of the Qur'an because they did not have time to do it alone at home. Apart from following the list of practices, the participants were also able to correct their recitation and practice it when reading the Qur'an by themselves. Furthermore, there was a noticeable change in the participants' behavior in the classroom. The participants appeared to be happier and began making friends and chatting with other classmates.

The participants also stated:

“Teacher, at first, I felt like I had to do good... like praying and all that... but later on, I felt guilty if I missed it... now, I try to do all the good deeds that you mentioned.”

“I feel happy coming to school, Teacher... it's fun to have many friends, and I understand the work when we do it in a group...”

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, emotional stress issues among students need to be taken seriously as they have various negative effects on schools, families, and even the nation. According to the 9 pillars of the National Security Policy 2021-2025, the issue of emotional stress, or mental health, is related to pillar 8, which is People's Security. One of the 153 items in the National Security Matrix is the Strengthening of Mental Health and Resilience of the People. This clearly shows that the government takes this issue very seriously. It cannot be taken lightly, and efforts to detect, prevent, and act must be carried out thoroughly by the involved parties. The Al-Ghazali Counseling Theory approach applied by the researcher in this study appears successful in addressing the emotional stress issues experienced by the participants. This is because the religious approach is the best way to improve the health and well-being of a person, both spiritually and physically. This includes strengthening faith and worship to Allah SWT, increasing acts of worship like prayer, reading the Qur'an, remembering Allah, and making supplications. All these are remedies that can heal and calm the human soul. As Allah SWT says in Surah Ar-Ra'd, verse 28, which means: “(That is) those who believe and whose hearts find rest in the remembrance of Allah. Verily, in the remembrance of Allah do hearts find rest.” This verse clarifies that remembering Allah brings peace. The tranquility of the heart will arise when humans can remember Allah's greatness, signs of His power, and the blessings He gives to His servants. Therefore, all parties must take responsibility in helping to address the issue of emotional stress among students, especially families, teachers, and schools. This is to ensure that students receive the necessary support, guidance, and attention to foster good emotional health and help them manage their emotions well. The researcher hopes that this study can assist other researchers and teachers in managing emotional stress among students.

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Rujukan

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